

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITE PIPES SUBJECTED TO UNDERGROUND BLASTS

William Toh¹, Karthikayen Raju¹, Chong Hun Yeo², Siang Huat Goh² and Vincent Beng Chye Tan¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, National University of Singapore, Singapore

² Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, National University of Singapore, Singapore

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we explore the response of fibreglass reinforced plastic (FRP) composite pipes when subjected to underground blasts. This is done through both numerical analysis using Finite Element Analysis and experimental verification using a scaled-down blast, by means of a centrifuge-scale model. Finite element modelling allows us to predict the response of the pipe and soil during actual blasts, which thus streamlines the design optimization process. However, the high costs of performing blast tests at realistic scales inhibits the large scale testing and verification of the finite element model. The use of a centrifuge blast experiment allows for low-cost experimental verification as the amount of explosives required in centrifuge blasts are scaled in a cubic relation with the length scale ratio. This allows for a larger number of tests that can be carried out in order to verify the numerical model developed.

The experimental set up consists of a stainless steel tank filled with 380mm of dry sand, with a 0.72g PETN explosive charge placed in the geometric centre of the tank, 100mm below the surface. A 56mm diameter filament wound FRP pipe buried with its central axis at the same level as the charge, 150mm away from the charge. The ends of the pipe are capped with PVC caps to keep the volume within the pipe void. Strain gauges are placed at locations on the pipe springline and crown to capture pipe responses. Pressure sensors are placed in the same plane as the charge and pipe central axes to capture soil responses.

In the finite element analysis, the Coupled Eulerian Lagrangian (CEL) analysis is employed to model the centrifuge experiment according to actual dimensions measured from the experimental setup. CEL analysis was chosen in place of a pure Lagrangian analysis due to the large amounts of deformation that would be present near the charge region, potentially causing excessive distortion in Lagrangian elements. The Eulerian mesh consists of soil and explosive charge, modelled using the extended Drucker-Prager Cap plasticity model and Jones-Wilkins-Lee (JWL) material models respectively. The composite pipe is modelled using Lagrangian continuum shell elements, incorporating orthotropic elastic properties together with Hashin's failure criteria for monitoring the health of the pipe after blast.

1 INTRODUCTION

In rapidly developing land scarce cities, such as Singapore, it is not uncommon to build structures with higher Gross Plot Ratios (ratio of Gross Floor Area to land area of site). One way to increase the Gross Plot Ratio is to build structures downwards into the underground. Some examples of massive underground structures include the Jurong Rock Caverns, which have managed to free up 60ha of land [1], and underground Mass Rapid Transit systems, which go up to depths of 42m [2]. To further maximise land usage, plots of land can be partitioned depth-wise to provide for different utilities which require different depths, encompassing up to 5 different utilities, such as pipes, rail and sewerage systems [3].

In the design of subsurface structures, various factors come into play, depending of the purpose of the structure and the possible types of loading scenarios that the structures will be subjected to. In

view of rising global threats of terrorism, there is a need to study the susceptibility of underground structures to threats such as bomb blasts. Of particular concern in the current work, is the effects of blasts on buried pipelines, which form a large part of the underground infrastructure. In recent years, utilization of composite materials as the choice material over traditional steel materials has seen a steady increase. This is due to the various advantages that composite materials present over steel, which include high strength to weight ratio, low coefficient of thermal expansion and resistance to corrosion [4-6].

Centrifuge modeling has been increasingly recognized as a powerful technique for modeling the behavior of soils under static and dynamic loading conditions. Centrifuge model testing allows in situ stresses in prototype (full-scale) structures to be reproduced in model tests. The first Geotechnical Centrifuge tests were conducted in the 1930s independently in the United States and Russia. Today, there are over 30 large centrifuges throughout the world being used for geotechnical engineering investigations.

In this work, the effects of a subsurface blast on a buried pipe is studied, both experimentally and numerically, with the purpose of developing suitable simulation tools for such niche purposes. Due to the large scale of the actual underground piping systems, the geotechnical centrifuge test is used to downsize the scale of experiment to be conducted. Numerical simulation of the centrifuge blast test was performed using the Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian (CEL) analysis, performed through commercial finite element software Abaqus/Explicit 6.14-2.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Centrifuge testing allows the prototype's in situ stresses to be reproduced in the model by placing the scaled model in an elevated gravitational field produced by the rotation of the centrifuge. Table 1 lists some of the relevant scaling laws for Geotechnical Centrifuge testing where N equals the centrifuge's induced acceleration divided by the prototype's gravitational acceleration. The scaling laws predict that the soil's total stress, pore water pressure, effective stress, particle velocity, strain, and density are the same for both the centrifuge scale models and the prototype.

An explosion is fundamentally a volumetric phenomenon and it has been established that the effects of a blast are related to the third power of the gravitational acceleration involved. A smaller mass of explosive, in a model detonated at a proportionately higher gravitational acceleration will have the same effects as a full-scale prototype explosive, detonated under the earth's normal gravitational field. For example, a 1g TNT charge tested under a 50g centrifugal acceleration field is equivalent to a 125 kg TNT charge under prototype conditions.

Quantity	Centrifuge	Prototype (Actual)
Stress	1	1
Strain	1	1
Stress wave velocity	1	1
Particle velocity	1	1
Density	1	1
Water pressure	1	1
Linear dimension	1	N
Dynamic time	1	N
Hydrodynamic time	1	N^2
Area	1	N^2
Force	1	N^2
Volume	1	N^3
Energy	1	N^3
Gravity	1	$1/N$
Acceleration	1	$1/N$
Unit weight	1	$1/N$
Cube root scaled distance	1	1

Table 1: Centrifuge scaling laws.

The pipe, with 8 strain gauges attached and ends capped with PVC caps, is placed at a level with about 38cm of sand below the central axis, alongside 3 accelerometers (Ch1-Ch3) and 6 pressure sensors (Ch4-Ch9). In addition, 720mg of PETN (equivalent to 90kg of PETN in actual prototype scale) was placed in the same plane, 15cm (equivalent to 7.5m in actual prototype scale) away from the centre of the pipe. Figure 1 shows the positions of the sensors and detonator relative to the pipe. Following the placement of the pipe and sensors, the sand layer is built up by another 10 cm (equivalent to 5m in actual prototype scale) to reach its final level.

Figure 1: (a) Position of soil sensors and detonator in the plane of the pipe central axis, (b) position of strain gauges on the outer surface of the pipe.

3 NUMERICAL MODEL

Due to large deformations that occur during the explosion, Lagrangian finite element meshes tend to undergo severe distortion during the simulation process and as a result, causes the analysis to terminate prematurely. Therefore, a Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian (CEL) analysis is performed, in which the soil and detonator are modelled with an Eulerian mesh, whereas the other components, i.e. pipe and caps, are modeled using Lagrangian elements. Symmetry about the vertical centre plane is assumed. A quarter model is not utilized due to the anisotropy of the composite pipe, which has alternating layers of laminae inclined at $\pm 55^\circ$ about the axis of the pipe. Figure 2 shows the centrifuge model, with the red portion representing soil and blue representing a void volume above the soil. The pipe, along with its end caps are encompassed in the model as well.

Figure 2: Geometry of the centrifuge model with half symmetry assumed.

3.1 Material properties

The composite pipe is modelled using the composite layup option available in Abaqus, with two sets of elastic ply properties used in the simulation. The first being properties obtained from literature under static conditions, the second being properties under dynamic loading. For both set of ply properties, the Hashin criteria for damage initiation is used in conjunction with softening damage evolution law. The properties used are given in Table 2.

	Elastic Properties		Strength properties [7]		Fracture energy [8]	
	Static [9]	Dynamic [10]	X_T (MPa)	1700	G_{ft}	12.5
E_1 (MPa)	39400	138600	X_C (MPa)	800	G_{fc}	12.5
E_2 (MPa)	8000	23500	Y_T (MPa)	30	G_{mt}	1.0
E_3 (MPa)	8000	23500	Y_C (MPa)	120	G_{mc}	1.0
G_{12} (MPa)	4000	4000	S_L (MPa)	57		
G_{23} (MPa)	4000	4000	S_T (MPa)	57		
G_{13} (MPa)	4000	4000				
ν_{12}	0.3	0.3				
ν_{13}	0.3	0.3				
ν_{23}	0.4	0.4				

Table 2: Ply properties of FRP used in simulations.

In modelling the soil, the modified Drucker-Prager cap plasticity model is used, with material properties given in Table 3.

Physical properties		Cap plasticity parameters [11]		Cap hardening	
Density, ρ (ton/mm ³)	1.73×10^{-9}	Cohesion (MPa)	1×10^{-5}	Yield stress	Volumetric plastic strain
		Friction angle (°)	43	0.6875	0
		Cap eccentricity	2.45	1.208	0.02
Elastic properties		Initial yield surface position	0.056	1.287	0.04
Young's modulus, E (MPa)	50	Transition surface radius	0.01	15.5	0.08
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.3	Flow stress ratio	1		

Table 3: Material properties for soil using the Modified Drucker Prager Cap plasticity model.

The detonator is modelled using the Jones-Wilkin-Lee (JWL) equation of state (EOS) model, with material properties given in Table 4 [12-14].

Quantity	Value	Quantity	Value	Quantity	Value
v_D (mm/s)	8.75×10^6	ω	0.25	E_0 (J/tonne)	5.7×10^{12}
A (MPa)	6.17×10^5	R_1	4.4	$G_{\text{pre-detonation}}$ (MPa)	9690
B (MPa)	1.6926×10^4	R_2	1.2	ρ (tonne/mm ³)	1.77×10^{-9}

Table 4: Material properties for PETN

The PVC cap is modelled using linear isotropic elastic material properties, with a Young's modulus of 3150MPa, Poisson's ratio of 0.4 and mass density of 1.45×10^{-9} tonne/mm³.

3.2 Boundary conditions and contact interactions

The curved exterior surface of the Eulerian mesh is assigned Eulerian boundary conditions of zero inflow and equilibrium outflow, while the base and symmetric surfaces are assigned zero normal velocity.

Contact between the pipe and PVC cap is modelled with surface-to-surface interactions. Contact between the Lagrangian surfaces and Eulerian surfaces is enforced using general contact. All contact properties were modelled with normal hard contact and tangential contact with penalty friction formulation, using values of 0.3 and 0.4 for the coefficients of friction respectively.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the CEL analysis, the response of soil can be captured without any convergence issues due to excessive distortion within the near field. This allows us to have contour plots alongside an actual soil geometry which has undergone significant amounts of distortion due to cratering by the blast, as well as upheaving of soil at the surface. Figure 3 shows the propagation of pressure in the soil, at the mid-plane of the soil, parallel to the pipe axis. It is observed that the cratering and upheaving of the soil are both predicted using the current model. In addition, wave reflection at soil boundaries are also observed.

A peak stress of 217MPa is recorded in the soil at the region immediately adjacent to the charge. The peak pressure decreases very rapidly to below 1MPa within fractions of a millisecond, as indicated by the non-red contours. Likewise, a crater of 80mm diameter is formed within the first millisecond, resulting in upheave of soil (Figure 3(c)-(f)).

Figure 3: Stress wave propagation in soil

Figure 4 shows the combined contour plots of stress states in the pipe (Figure 4(a)) and soil (Figure 4(b)), at the level of the pipe central axis. The stress wave propagates through the soil and reaches the pipe at about 0.05ms (Figure 4(c)). Upon interaction with the pipe, the stress wave is then seen to be reflected back, as indicated by the dark red region in Figure 4(d). The pipe acts to redistribute the soil stress along the entire pipe length, as seen by the wider contours beyond the pipe in Figure 4(e).

Figure 4: Contour plots of soil in plane of pipe centre axis and top view of pipe.

In the present work, the focus is on the response of the composite pipes. Therefore, the pressures and accelerations recorded by the soil pressure sensors and accelerometers will not be discussed in further detail. What is interesting to observe in the pipe is the non-homogeneity of stress along the pipe length. This is due to the anisotropy of the pipe, which has orthotropic plies stacked at $\pm 55^\circ$ oblique to the central axis. The anisotropy is further illustrated in Figure 5, which shows the different orientations of stress distributions between odd and even plies at $t = 0.06\text{ms}$. It is also evident in Figure 5, that the innermost and outermost plies experience the highest magnitudes of stress. This is indicated by the dark red regions at the crown position (the centre of the pipe in the images) for Plies 1 and 2 and at the springline facing blast (bottom of the pipe in the images) for Plies 11 and 12.

Figure 5: Mises stress contours for individual plies at $t = 0.06\text{ms}$ as viewed from above. Contours follow the same legend as Figure 4(a).

In validating the model and material parameters, we compare strain gauge readings obtained experimentally with numerical results from simulations performed with both static and dynamic pipe properties. Comparing strain gauge readings with strains obtained with static pipe properties, it is evident that there is severe over-prediction of the pipe responses, with predicted peak strain values more than double of experimental observations. However, when dynamic properties are used, the correlation between experiment and simulation shows relatively good agreement. One point to note about the experimental strain response is the difference in arrival times of the waves, resulting in the strain profiles being displaced temporally with each other. This is due to experimental issues that are associated with defining the exact trigger time.

Figure 6: Strain readings at various channels.

Throughout the duration of the blast, the maximum stress experienced by any of the plies is 89.0MPa and 19.9MPa in the fibre (σ_{11}) and matrix (σ_{22}) directions respectively. These stresses are much lower than the ply failure strengths given in Table 2, which implies that the pipes are undamaged after the blast. This may be confirmed by the zero values of damage variables (namely DAMAGEMT, DAMAGEMC, DAMAGEFC, DAMAGEFT) throughout the entire pipe, after the blast.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The effects of a subsurface blast on a buried composite pipe is studied in this work, both experimentally and numerically. The experimental investigation utilized the centrifuge, which employs rotational centrifugal forces to replicate a scaled down model, allowing for testing under controlled laboratory conditions. A finite element model of the centrifuge test was created using CEL analysis to validate material models used for mainly the FRP pipe and sand.

It was shown that the CEL model is able to provide detailed insights of soil and pipe responses due to the blast, detailing the crater formation and upheave in soil, soil-pipe interaction and anisotropic behaviour of the composite pipe. Simulation results were compared with strain gauge readings obtained from the centrifuge test to validate the appropriate use of various material models and parameters in the simulation. It was found that the model was able to predict the pipe response reasonably accurately.

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